

ABOUT PESTS OF GOURDS IN THE SAMARKAND REGION

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ABSTRACT

Abstract: When obtaining sustainable high yields of gourds, one of the main obstacles is the presence of a large number of pests on them. Of these, the following representatives are of particular danger: winter, exclamation and cotton scoops, gamma scoop, greenhouse whitefly, common spider mite, melon aphid, sprout fly, meadow moth, common bear, gall nematodes, tobacco thrips, melon fly, wireworms.

Key words: Melon growing, melons and watermelons of Uzbekistan, insect pests, melon fly (*Myopardalis pardalina*), melon ladybug (*Epilachna chrysomelina*), gourd or cotton aphid (*Aphis gossypii*), damage by crops of melon and pumpkin vegetable crops, protective measures.

INTRODUCTION

In Uzbekistan, melon growing is the oldest industry. Here, melons were cultivated as early as the 4th century BC. Even in the Middle Ages, melon fruits were exported from Uzbekistan to many foreign countries. In 2011, according to the Ministry of Agriculture and Water Resources of the Republic, melons and gourds in Uzbekistan were cultivated on an area of 74113 hectares, and the gross harvest of fruits amounted to 1 million 572 thousand tons.

Of these, watermelon occupied 36359 ha or 49.9%, melon 28957 ha or 39.1% and pumpkin 8797 ha or 11.8%. Gross yields of watermelon amounted to 770896 tons or 49%, melons - 580803 tons or 37.5% and pumpkins - 220037 tons or 14%. The yield of watermelon was 21.2 t/ha, melon - 20.1 t/ha and pumpkin - 25.0 t/ha.

METHODOLOGY

The place of research was specialized farms for the cultivation of vegetable and melon crops located in the Zeravshan oasis of Uzbekistan for 2020-2022. The analysis used generally accepted entomological, ecological and mathematical-statistical methods.

The collection of biomaterials was carried out according to the method of Golub V.B. (1980) and Adashkevich B.P. (1983)

Myiopardalis pardalina is not included in the list of quarantine species in Uzbekistan, but is an internal quarantine species. The melon fly was first discovered in 1891 in Pakistan and Iran. It was later reported that it had spread to Azerbaijan. The distribution of the species accelerated by the 1960s with migration to Azerbaijan, Armenia, Georgia, the Caucasus, Krasnodar and Stavropol in the west, India in the east, and Afghanistan in the south. In the period from 1965 to 1966, there was a massive increase in the cultivation of gourds in Azerbaijan [2].

The period when the melon fly harms is the period of the larva, which pierces the body of the fetus. Melon tissue that has died as a result of malnutrition turns a dark brown color and the resulting odor spreads to the melon. The taste and aroma of the fruit deteriorate. When the adult larvae leave the melon, they cause tissue damage through the holes they open and quickly spread throughout the body. Thus, the damage is further increased. Melons are inedible and have lost their commercial value.

Various studies carried out in our country have shown that melon flies are harmful as a result of feeding on melons. However, there is no analysis of how the fruit and its flavor deteriorate. We are also doing research on this issue.

The melon cow or epilachna (*Epilachna chrysomelina*) belongs to the family of Coccinellid beetles (ladybugs). It is distributed mainly in Central Asia and the Caucasus, especially dangerous in Tajikistan and Turkmenistan. In the southern regions of Uzbekistan, this species is very harmful.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Melons are assigned to the pumpkin family (*Cucurbitaceae*) and consist of three related species with biological and morphological differences. Of these, melons (*Cucumis melo L.*), watermelons (*Citrullus lanatus L.*), pumpkin (*Cucurbita pepo L.*) are widely cultivated in Uzbekistan. [3].

According to some data in Uzbekistan, the melon fly is common in Karakalpakstan, Khorezm, Bukhara, Jizzakh, Syrdarya and Tashkent regions. [1]. However, our scientific observations show that this pest is also widespread in the Samarkand region.

Watermelon, melon and pumpkin are heat-resistant crops. Watermelon is more demanding of heat, pumpkin is less so. Melon, although less demanding of heat than watermelon, is the most heat-resistant. Therefore, melon is more widely grown in the Central Asian region, and watermelon - in the south of Russia and Ukraine. Pumpkin seeds begin to germinate at 12 °C, melons - 15 °C and watermelon - 16-17 °C. The

best temperature for seed germination is 25-32 °C. At 35-40 °C, seed germination is significantly reduced.

CONCLUSION

For effective implementation of protective measures, it is necessary to know the species composition, the annual development cycle, the conditions that promote and suppress the development of pests and pathogens, their harmfulness, methods and means of combating them.

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